

Experimental comparison of two solar-driven air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers: Indirect versus direct air-cooled system

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Abstract

Experiments were run to compare an indirectly air-cooled commercial absorption chiller to a directly air-cooled absorption chiller prototype. Both were 4.5-kW, 1-m³, single-effect LiBr–H₂O chillers. The trials were conducted at outdoor dry bulb temperatures ranging from 28 to 37 °C. The maximum allowable generator inlet temperature in the commercial chiller (to prevent salt crystallisation) was 105 °C, while in the prototype it was 120 °C. The commercial chiller delivered chilled water at 18 °C and the prototype at 16 °C. The mean daily COP_{th} was 0.55 in the commercial chiller, compared to 0.62 in the prototype. The mean daily COP_{elec} for the chiller and prototype was 3.5 and 5.3, respectively. The mean daily SCOP for the solar-powered air conditioning facility was around 0.08 in both cases.

Keywords: Absorption, LiBr/H₂O, Solar cooling, Experimental, Directly air-cooled, Indirectly air-cooled

1. Introduction

Progress has been made in solar collector-powered sorption chiller systems in recent years on the back of efforts to protect the environment and the technological development of new components and systems [1,2]. Absorption chillers are an example of technology attempts to mitigate both the dependence on electricity, especially during summertime overloads, and the environmental harm caused by greenhouse gases [3]. A great deal of numerical and experimental studies on solar-powered air conditioning using LiBr/H₂O absorption technology are available today [4–13]. All the LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers currently on the market are water-cooled. The drawback to water-cooled systems lies in the cooling towers, which imply problems in residential buildings, water consumption and entail maintenance costs, not to mention the likelihood of *Legionella* infection. Air-cooled systems avoid the problems associated with cooling towers. Nonetheless, other concerns associated with their use need to be taken into consideration, such as the larger heat exchange area required, and the possibility of salt crystallisation due to the high absorption and condensation temperatures reached when the outdoor temperature is very high [14]. Ample research has been conducted and published on the improvement of air-cooled systems and attempts to prevent crystallisation [15–22]. In air-cooled absorption chillers, the absorption and condensation heat can be transferred to the outdoor air either indirectly (via re-cooling, e.g. wet, dry and hybrid) or directly. Kim and Infante-Ferreira [23] reported simulation findings for two LiBr–H₂O half-effect chillers, one directly and the other indirectly air-cooled. At outdoor temperatures of 35–50 °C, the indirect system exhibited lower COP and cooling capacity values than the directly cooled system. To date, to the best of authors' knowledge, only one air-cooled single effect LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller has ever been marketed and was available from 2005 to

2008 [24]. Lizarte et al. [25] tested for 10 summer days an innovative directly air-cooled absorption chiller prototype, and promising results were obtained. But as far as the authors know, no empirical comparison of these two types of air-cooled absorption chillers is to be found in the literature, however.

The aim sought in this study is to compare the performance of the *indirectly air-cooled* single-effect LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller ever marketed and the *directly air-cooled* absorption chiller prototype. Both of them have similar specifications and were designed for residential use. In both cases the heat source and the room to be air-conditioned are the same. The two chillers were analysed from the standpoint of their external fluids.

2. Description of the solar-cooling absorption system

It is located in the Heat Pump Laboratory owned by the Eduardo Torroja Institute for Construction Science (a body of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)) in Arganda del Rey, a town on the outskirts of Madrid, Spain. As shown in Fig. 1, the facility consisted of a solar thermal plant, an air-cooled single effect LiBr/H₂O absorption chiller (commercial or prototype) and a fan coil in the room to be cooled. The indoor comfort temperature (t_{in}) was set at 23–25 °C, the range specified in the Spanish Regulations for Thermal Facilities in Buildings (RITE) in effect in 2009 [26].

Fig. 1. Solar cooling absorption system.

The solar cooling facility using the indirectly air-cooled commercial chiller, hereafter SCF IAC C, was tested in the summer of 2008, and the solar cooling facility using the directly air-cooled prototype, hereafter SCF DAC P, in the summer of 2009.

2.1. Solar thermal plant

The three circuits comprising this facility and their main components are described below.

- The *primary circuit* consisted of a field of vacuum flat-plate solar collectors with a total aperture area of 42.2 m², an angle over the horizontal of from 0° to 30°, a 295-W pump (P_1) and the hot side of a 25-kW plate heat exchanger (PHE). This circuit, which carried a 30% ethyleneglycol solution in water, had a mass flow rate of $m_{fcol} = 0.47$ kg/s.
- The *secondary circuit* comprised the cold side of the PHE, a 175-W pump (P_2) and a 1.5-m³ storage tank. The mass flow rate in this circuit, which carried a 10% ethyleneglycol solution in water, was $m_{fsec} = 0.36$ kg/s.
- The *tertiary circuit* components included the storage tank, a 110-W pump (P_3) and the absorption chiller generator. The solution was pumped from the tank to the generator. An 11-kW dry cooler

rejected the excess heat to the outdoor air.

Further information on the solar facility components is given in Ref. [24].

2.2. Absorption chillers

2.2.1. Indirectly air-cooled system

This 4.5-kW chiller (Rotartica 045v), which used LiBr–H₂O pair as working fluid and occupied a volume of approximately 1 m³, was initially brought to market in 2005 but is no longer available. Its operation was based on essentially the same processes as any other single effect absorption chiller [3]. Fig. 2 contains a simplified diagram of its main components. It used the rotating absorption technology developed by Interotex in the 1990s, consisting of placing the generator, absorber, evaporator and condenser, i.e., the components where the working fluid underwent phase changes, in a hermetically welded spheroid container that is rotated by a motor around a horizontal axis to increase heat and mass transfer in its components [27,28].

This chiller rejected heat via re-cooling with a dry fan coil unit and a pump (P_{wcool}). The coolant water was first pumped to the absorber coil and then to the condenser coil, where its temperature rose as it received the absorption (Q_a) and condensation (Q_c) heat. This water subsequently transferred the sum of Q_a and Q_c to the outdoor air through the dry fan coil unit.

Fig. 3 shows a diagram in which it is explained, from a qualitative point of view, how the temperature of the working fluids varies: the solution and the coolant water in the absorber, the refrigerant and the coolant water in the condenser, and the coolant water and the air in the fan-coil.

The chiller was fitted with three hydraulic circuits: hot, chilled and absorber–condenser coolant. It also used outdoor air.

Fig. 2. Diagram showing the indirectly air-cooled chiller (commercial).

- *Hot fluid circuit:* the hot circuit fed the generator with sufficient heat power and temperature to trip chiller operation. According to manufacturer's specifications, the requirements for chiller operation were $t_{ig} \geq 80$ °C, $m_g \geq 0.17$ kg/s and the existence of a cooling load. The chiller shut down when the t_{ig} was under 76 °C. For safety reasons, the t_{ig} could be no higher than 105 °C.
- *Chilled water circuit:* the chilled water circuit fulfilled the ultimate purpose of the chiller. A pump built into the chiller drove the water through the evaporator (m_{chill}), where it was chilled, and subsequently pumped to the fan coil in the room to be air conditioned. The manufacturer specified a minimum m_{chill} of 0.33 kg/s.
- *Coolant water circuit:* this circuit received the Q_a and Q_c , which it transferred to the outside air in the dry fan coil. The water was driven by a pump built into the chiller. The manufacturer's recommended $m_{cool} \leq 0.5$ kg/s.

- *Outdoor air*: outdoor air (m_{air}) was fanned across the dry fan coil, where it received the Q_a and Q_c from the coolant water circuit.

Fig. 3. Qualitative variation of the working fluids temperature (commercial).

2.2.2. Directly air-cooled system

Built at the aforementioned Heat Pump Laboratory (CSIC), the prototype is protected under a patent [29]. This single-double effect, LiBr–H₂O prototype occupies 1 m³ (Fig. 4). Its design capacity is 4.5 kW when operating in single effect mode and 7 kW in double effect mode. Fig. 5 shows the prototype in single effect mode. When operating in single effect mode, its main components include a generator, a condenser, an evaporator, a flat-fan sheet adiabatic absorber [20,30], a heat regenerator (PHE), two solution pumps, a solution/air finned tube heat exchanger (FTHE) and a fan. The prototype transfers Q_a and Q_c to the outdoor air as follows (see Fig. 5): the LiBr/H₂O solution enters the absorber in the form of flat-fan sheets (10, 13). As the refrigerant vapour condenses on the sheets, the solution concentration (X , %) declines and the temperature rises, because vapour absorption is an exothermal process that takes place adiabatically. The solution is then pumped from the absorber to the FTHE (11), where forced convection is used to reject the Q_a to the outdoor air. Lastly, after it is sub-cooled in the FTHE, the solution returns to the absorber (13).

Fig. 4. Directly air-cooled prototype.

The air, in turn, after receiving the Q_a , flows through the condenser. There, the refrigerant, in the form of an overheated vapour flowing in from the generator (1), rejects first the sensible heat (until the saturation temperature is reached) and then the latent heat to the outdoor air, Q_c .

Fig. 6 shows a diagram in which it is explained, from a qualitative point of view, how the temperature of the solution and the air in the FTHE, and the temperature of the refrigerant and the air in the condenser vary.

When comparing Figs. 3–6 it is observed that the commercial chiller has an intermediate fluid (coolant water), and because of it, there are two additional differences of temperature, one between the coolant water and the condensation temperature, and the other one, between the coolant water and the absorption temperature.

Fig. 5. Diagram showing the directly air-cooled prototype (single effect mode).

Fig. 6. Qualitative variation of the working fluids temperature (prototype).

The controls for the prototype were manual. The mass flow rate of the solution pumped to the generator (m_{sol}) was raised with rising t_{ig} and t_{odb} .

The external fluids were two hydraulic circuits, hot and chilled, plus the outdoor air.

- *Hot circuit:* the hot liquid was pumped from the storage tank to the generator, where it transferred heat, Q_g . The minimum t_{ig} required to begin to produce cold was determined by the t_{odb} and t_c . This value was obtained with the Dühring diagram, and assuming a 10 °C difference between the final boiling temperature and the t_{ig} . Where the $t_{odb} = 35$ °C and the $t_c = 10$ °C, for instance, if the $t_a = 40$ °C and the $t_c = 45$ °C, the minimum t_{ig} would be 84 °C. Moreover, the prototype can be fed with temperatures of up to 120°C, when the $t_c = 50$ °C and the $t_e = 10$ °C (24).
- *Chilled circuit:* water was chilled in the evaporator, fulfilling the ultimate purpose of the chiller.
- *Outdoor air:* driven by a fan, it received the Q_a and Q_c directly, which raised its temperature from t_{odb} to t_{air} .

3. Environmental and process variables

Since these facilities used solar energy as a heat source, two clear days with maximum solar irradiance on the tilted surface on the order of 1000 W/m² were chosen for the comparison. Since the two chillers to be compared were air cooled, the two days chosen were selected for their very high (and similarly patterned) outdoor dry bulb temperatures (t_{odb}). Wind speed was also similar on the two days, for this factor affected heat loss in the collectors and the facility as a whole (31). The meteorological variables were recorded at a weather station.

The working days chosen were 25 August 2008 for the SCF_IAC_C and 28 August 2009 for the SCF_DAC_P. Fig. 7 shows the solar irradiance on the collectors on those two days (G_t).

Fig. 7. Solar irradiance on the tilted surface on *the test* days.

The maximum t_{odb} on 25 August was 36.5°C, and on 28 August 37.7°C (Fig. 8). This figure also shows the cooling load (Q_{cd}) on the two days. Q_{cd} was calculated as described by Izquierdo et al. (32). The working day began at 07:00 and ended at 19:00. A cooling load was first recorded at approximately 09:00. The cooling energy demand (E_{cd}) during working hours on 25 August 2008 was 42kWh and on 28 August 2009, 43.5 kWh.

The mean wind speed during working hours was 1.4m/s on 25 August and 1 m/s on 28 August (Fig.9).

The process variables recorded were the temperatures and mass flow rates summarised in Table 1. The instruments used to record the process variables were PT100-type rated thermal resistors, whose readings were stored by the minute with a data acquisition system. The fluid mass flow rates were measured with ultrasonic flowmeters and the air flow with an anemometer. The pressure in the prototype evaporator was measured with a pressure sensor and the evaporation temperature was obtained from the evaporation pressure and properties of the water (33). The accuracy of the sensors is given in Table 2.

Fig. 8. Outdoor dry bulb temperature and cooling load on the two test days.

Fig.9. Wind speed on the test days.

Table 1- Process variables.

	Temperature (°C)	Mass flow rate (kg/s)
Solar facility	$t_{scol}, t_{icol}, t_{itank}, t_{otank}$	m_{fcol}, m_{fsec}
Commercial chiller and prototype	$t_{ig}, t_{og}, t_{ie}, t_{oe}, t_{oair}$	m_g, m_{chill}, m_{air}
Commercial chiller	t_{wcool}, t_{owcool}	m_{cool}
Prototype	t_a, t_c, t_e	
Fancoil (room)	t_{in}, t_{oairc}	

Table 2- Transducer accuracy.

Device	Accuracy
Thermal resistance	± 0.1 °C
Data acquisition system	± 0.05 of reading
Ultrasonic flowmeter	$\pm 1-3\%$ of reading
Anemometer	± 0.01 m/s
Pressure sensor	0.2% FS

4. Data reduction

The energy balances in the solar cooling facility are shown next, along with the collector performance, the COP and the SCOP.

4.1. Solar thermal plant

The solar power on the tilted surface (Q_t) was obtained from Eq. (1).

$$Q_t = A_{col} \cdot G_t \quad (1)$$

From dawn and until P_2 began to operate, the Q_t was transformed into heat, part of which accumulated in the primary circuit components, raising their temperature. The remainder was transferred to the outdoor air by convection and radiation (31). This energy ($H_{t,min}$) was not used in the process (i.e., did not produce useful heat), but was nonetheless required to raise the primary circuit fluid to the temperature needed to switch on P_2 .

The power transferred to the thermal fluid inside the collectors while P_2 was in operation was calculated from Eq. (2)

$$Q_{fcol} = m_{fcol} \cdot Cp_{fcol} \cdot (t_{ocol} - t_{icol}) \quad (2)$$

During that time, the primary circuit fluid transferred heat to the secondary circuit fluid which rejected it, in turn, to the storage tank. The power supplied to the storage tank was found with Eq. (3)

$$Q_{itank} = m_{fsec} \cdot Cp_{fsec} \cdot (t_{itank} - t_{otank}) \quad (3)$$

Finally, the solar energy between P_2 shutdown and when Q_t reached zero ($H_{t,losses}$) was not used in the process.

The daily mean collector performance ($\eta_{col,mean}$) was obtained with Eq. 4), as the ratio between the energy transferred to thermal fluid inside the collectors (E_{fcol}) and the solar energy on the tilted surface (E_t).

$$\eta_{col,mean} = \frac{E_{fcol}}{E_t} \quad (4)$$

4.2. Absorption chillers

The heat delivered by the solar facility to the generator (Q_g), the cooling capacity obtained in the evaporator (Q_e) and the heat rejected by the absorber and the condenser to the outdoor air (Q_{a+c}) were found with Eqs. (5)–(7), respectively.

$$Q_g = m_g \cdot Cp_{mg} \cdot (t_{ig} - t_{og}) \quad (5)$$

$$Q_e = m_{chill} \cdot Cp_w \cdot (t_{oe} - t_{ie}) \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{a+c} = m_{air} \cdot Cp_{air} \cdot (t_{oair} - t_{odb}) \quad (7)$$

The instantaneous COP_{th} was calculated from Eq. (8)

$$COP_{th} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_g} \quad (8)$$

Eq. (9) was used to calculate the COP in terms of primary energy ($COP_{prim,E}$), where W_{elec} is the electric power of the ancillary equipment and η_{conv} the primary energy – electric power conversion factor, which in Spain was around 0.38 in 2008 and 2009 [34].

$$COP_{prim,E} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_g + (W_{elec}/\eta_{conv})} \quad (9)$$

Finally, COP_{elec} was obtained from Eq. (10)

$$\text{COP}_{\text{elec}} = \frac{Q_e}{W_{\text{elec}}} \quad (10)$$

4.3. Solar cooling facility

The instantaneous solar coefficient of performance (SCOP) is obtained from Eq. (11)

$$\text{SCOP} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_t} \quad (11)$$

5. Results

5.1. Solar thermal plant

Fig. 10 shows the collector inlet and outlet temperatures, and the tank inlet and outlet temperatures from and to the secondary circuit. Fig. 11 shows the Q_t , Q_{fcol} and Q_{itank} for the two facilities (SCF_IAC_C and SCF_DAC_P). The daily energy (E_t , E_{fcol} and E_{itank}) is the area underneath the respective curve in Fig. 11.

Fig. 10. Collector: fluid temperatures. Tank: inlet/outlet temperatures from/to secondary circuit.

Fig. 11. Heat transfer rates (solar thermal plant).

Table 3 gives the most significant values found for the two facilities. According to Fig. 10 and Table 3,

while the working temperatures were around 10 °C higher in the SCF IAC C than in the SCF DAC P, η_{col_mean} was similar in the two facilities.

Table 3- Solar thermal plant variables (SCF_IAC_C and SFC_DAC_P).

	SCF_IAC_C (25/08/08)	SCF_DAC_P (28/08/09)
t_{ocol_max} (°C)	103.2	113
t_{itank_max} (°C)	91	104
H_t (kWh/m ²)	7.5	7.5
H_{t_min} (kWh/m ²)	0.5	0.7
H_{t_losses} (kWh/m ²)	0.9	1.1
E_{fcol} (kWh/m ²)	2.5	2.3
E_{itank} (kWh/m ²)	2.2	2.0
η_{col_mean}	0.33	0.31

5.2. Absorption chillers

The findings for the two chillers based on the external fluids in their main heat exchangers are discussed below.

5.2.1. Generator

Fig. 12 shows the generator inlet and outlet hot fluid temperatures, along with Q_g .

Fig. 12. Generator: temperatures and heat transfer rates.

5.2.1.1. Indirectly air-cooled system. The tank reached 80 °C at 10:00, when the hot fluid began to be pumped to the generator ($m_g = 0.2$ kg/s), setting off cold production. The t_{ig} rose from 80 °C to 95.5 °C as a result of the heat delivered by the solar collectors to the storage tank. When P_2 switched off (15:40), i.e., when heat ceased to be transferred from the collectors to the tank, the t_{ig} declined abruptly to 76 °C, the temperature at which the commercial chiller was designed to shut down. At the end of the working day, the tank temperature was approximately 76 °C. The mean Q_g was 8 kW and the total energy demanded by the chiller (E_g) was 55.5 kWh.

5.2.1.2. Directly air-cooled system. At 09:00, with Q_{cd} in the room and the storage tank temperature high enough to produce cold (90 °C), a constant flow of hot fluid was pumped to the generator ($m_g = 0.29$ kg/s). Thanks to the Q_{itank} , the t_{ig} rose to 106 °C, despite which the LiBr was not observed to crystallise. When P_2 switched off, the t_{ig} began to decline, dropping from 105 °C (15:10) to 97 °C (16:00). The experiment was regarded to come to an end at the latter time, since the prototype tended to produce less and less chilled water

as the t_{ig} descended, and was unable to provide the Q_e required to handle the Q_{cd} in the room. At the end of the working day, the tank temperature was approximately 97 °C. The mean Q_g was around 6 kW and $E_g = 40.1$ kWh.

Note that Q_g was higher in the commercial chiller. Moreover, the tank temperature at the end of the working day was higher in the SCF DAC P than in the SCF IAC C. Consequently, with the prototype, the solar thermal plant had higher feed temperatures the next day and was able to meet the early morning Q_{cd} .

5.2.2. Evaporator

Fig. 13 shows the evaporator inlet and outlet water temperatures and cooling capacities, along with the prototype t_e .

Fig. 13. Evaporator: temperatures and cooling capacities.

5.2.2.1. *Indirectly air-cooled system.* The m_{chill} was 0.47 kg/s. From 09:50 to 10:20, the water was chilled from 27.6 °C to 18 °C and the cold produced (E_e) came to 2.1 kWh. From 10:20 to 15:00, the t_{oe} steadied at around 18 °C while the t_{ig} rose with the t_{odb} (Figs. 8 and 12), and E_e was 2.3 kWh. From 15:00 until the chiller shut down (17:10), the t_{ig} declined from 95.5 to 76 °C, while the t_{odb} was around 36 °C and the t_{oe} rose to 21.3 °C. The E_e during that interval was 8.2 kWh.

While the t_{ig} was rising, the Q_e in the chiller remained approximately constant at around 4.5 kW, and declined as the t_{ig} fell. The daily E_e was 30.6 kWh, while the solar fraction (SF), defined as the ratio between the daily E_e and the E_{cd} during the working hours, in per cent, climbed to 73%.

5.2.2.2. *Directly air-cooled system.* The m_{chill} was 0.27 kg/s. The chilled water temperature (t_{oe}) at 09:20, 22 °C, dropped to 16 °C by 10:10. The prototype produced $E_e = 2.2$ kWh in those 50 min. From 10:10 to 15:10, the t_{oe} steadied at around 16 °C, while the t_{ig} rose with the t_{odb} , and E_e was 19.5 kWh. After 15:10, the t_{ig} began to decline and the t_{oe} to rise until the prototype shut down at 16:00, when the t_{oe} was 21.6 °C. E_e was 3.4 kWh in that period. The t_e was a flat 11 °C throughout the trial.

During the day, Q_e was observed to follow the same trend as Q_{cd} , up to a maximum of 4.5 kW. This was because the m_{sol} rose with rising t_{odb} and t_{ig} . When the t_{ig} began to decline, both the m_{sol} and the Q_e declined as well. The daily E_e was 25.1 kWh, while the SF amounted to 56%.

5.2.3. Absorber-condenser

Fig.14 shows the inlet and outlet air temperatures and the sum of the heat rejected in the two chillers (Q_{a+c}). It also shows the prototype condensation and absorption temperatures.

5.2.3.1. *Indirectly air-cooled system.* The mean m_{cool} was 0.58 kg/s. This water, after receiving first the Q_a and then the Q_c , entered the dry fan coil at a temperature (t_{owcool}) of around 10°C higher than the t_{odb} . After rejecting Q_{a+c} to the outdoor air, it returned to the absorber-condenser assembly at a temperature (t_{iwcool}) about 5°C higher than the t_{odb} . The air, in turn, with a mean mass flow rate of 1.72 kg/s, was 6 °C warmer after crossing the dry fan coil. Using Eq. (7), the total heat rejected to the outdoor air was calculated to be $E_{a+c} = 91$ kWh.

5.2.3.2. *Directly air-cooled system.* The mean m_{air} crossing the FTHE and the condenser was 1.67 kg/s. The temperature of this air, after receiving the Q_a and Q_c , rose by 5 °C. The t_a remained at 5 and 7 °C over the t_{odb} , while the t_e held at 10-11 °C over that temperature. The decline in the t_{ig} after 15:10 lowered the t_c and t_a as well. Finally, the heat rejected by the prototype came to $E_{a+c} = 64$ kWh.

The difference in the E_{e+a} values for the two chillers was due essentially to the greater E_g demanded by the commercial chiller generator.

Fig. 14. Absorber-condenser: air temperatures and total heat rejected. Prototype condensation and absorption temperatures.

5.2.4. Coefficient of performance

Fig. 15 shows the COP_{th} , COP_{prim_E} and COP_{elec} for the two chillers.

Fig.15. COP_{th} , COP_{prim_E} and COP_{elec}

5.2.4.1. *Indirectly air-cooled system.* The mean daily COP_{th} was 0.55. COP_{elec} and COP_{prim_E} were calculated by considering the electricity consumption of the chilled water circulation pump, the re-cooling system coolant circulation pump, the fan and the rotating drum, which came to 1200 W. The total electricity consumed by the chiller came to 6.6 kWh, or 17.4 kWh in terms of primary energy, yielding daily mean COP_{elec} and COP_{prim_E} values of 3.5 and 0.42, respectively.

5.2.4.2. *Directly air-cooled system.* The mean daily COP_{th} was 0.62. The ancillary components considered to calculate prototype COP_{elec} and COP_{prim_E} were the chilled water circulation pump, the two solution pumps and the fan, for a total of 700W. That brought the total electric energy consumed to 4.9 kWh or 12.8 kWh in terms of primary energy, and the mean daily COP_{elec} to 5.3 and the mean daily COP_{prim_E} to 0.47.

The COP_{th} value obtained with the prototype was higher than for the commercial chiller primarily because its generator had a lower Q_g . Up to 12:00, however, the COP_{th} values were similar. The explanation is as follows: up to that time, Q_{cd} rose from 0 to 4 kW. In that interval, the prototype adjusted its Q_e to the Q_{cd} , whereas the commercial chiller delivered a constant Q_e of 4.5 kW.

The COP_{elec} and COP_{prim_E} were also higher in the prototype because the commercial ancillary components demanded more electricity than the prototype components.

The prototype COP_{th} proved to be comparable with water-cooled, small-scale absorption chillers (1), while its mean daily COP_{elec} was similar to the performance specified in the main electrical-chiller catalogues (35).

5.3. Fan coil

Fig. 16 shows the indoor and the supply air temperatures (t_{in} , t_{oafc}).

5.3.1. SCF_IAC_C

The initial t_{in} was 27 °C. During the working day, while the t_{ig} rose with the t_{odb} , the t_{in} remained at around 23°C. The difference between the supply and indoor temperatures was around 3°C.

5.3.2. SCF_DAC_P

The initial t_{in} was 27 °C, which declined to around 25°C. The difference between supply and indoor temperatures was about 6°C. In other words, while the t_{in} attained with both facilities was within the range specified by Spanish legislation, the difference between the t_{in} and the t_{oafc} was smaller in the SCF_IAC_C than in the SCF_DAC_P. The implication is that, for a fan coil with the same capacity, the mass flow rate of the supply air must be greater in the former than in the latter. More specifically, the rate was 5400 m³/h in the SCF_IAC_C, and around 2160 m³/h in the SCF_DAC_P. A higher supply air flow rate leads to discomfort in the room.

5.4. Solar cooling facility

The instantaneous SCOP for the facilities fitted with the commercial chiller and the prototype is shown in Fig. 17.

5.4.1. SCF_IAC_C

The mean daily SCOP value was 0.09. From 5:40 to 10:00 and from 17:20 to 19:20, there was Q_t but the facility produced no cold ($Q_e = 0$ kW). As a result, the instantaneous SCOP values obtained were higher than the daily mean. Between 16:00 and 18:00 the SCOP rose from 0.11 to 0.21 because Q_t declined more steeply than Q_e .

Fig.16. Fan coil: air temperatures.

Fig. 17. Solar coefficient of performance.

5.4.2. *SCF_DAC_P*

The mean daily value was 0.08. As above, the daily mean was lower than the instantaneous values obtained during working hours.

The mean daily SCOP values obtained for the two facilities proved to be comparable to the performance for solar powered, water-cooled absorption chillers (5).

6. Conclusions

The only air-cooled single effect LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller ever marketed (and no longer available) used an indirect system. The present study compared that chiller to a prototype with similar specifications (single effect, 4.5-kW, 1-m³), but directly air-cooled. The two chillers were powered by a field of vacuum flat plate solar collectors with an aperture area of 9 m² per kW of cooling capacity.

The comparison of the two chillers showed the following.

Indirectly air-cooled system

- For safety reasons, the highest t_{ig} that could be used in the chiller was 105 °C. It started up at $t_{ig} = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$ and shut down at $t_{ig} = 76^{\circ}\text{C}$, regardless of the t_{odb} .
- The E_g required came to 55.5 kWh. Of the total cold output ($E_c = 30.6$ kWh), 6.7% was produced at chiller start-up when the t_{oe} ranged from 27 to 18 °C, 66.4% with a t_{oe} of around 18 °C and 27% with a t_{oe} of over 18 °C.
- When the t_{odb} ranged from 28.5 to 36.5°C and the t_{ig} from 82 to 95.4°C, the Q_e was approximately constant at 4.5 kW, the t_{oe} held at around 18 °C and the t_{j0} attained was within the limits established by the RITE, with a supply air mass flow rate on the order of 5400 m³/h.
- The mean daily COP_{th} was 0.55, the COP_{prim_E} was 0.42 and the COP_{elec} was 3.5.
- The maximum t_{ocol} was 103 °C, while the mean daily η_{col} was 0.33 and the mean daily SCOP 0.09.

Directly air-cooled system

- Even at feed temperatures of up to 120°C, with a t_c of 50 °C and a t_e of 10°C, the LiBr did not crystallise, nor did the prototype have to be enlarged.
- The generator demanded $E_g = 40.1$ kWh. Of the total cold produced ($E_c = 25.1$ kWh), 8.6 % was produced at chiller start-up when the t_{oe} ranged from 22°C to 16°C; 77.7% was produced with a t_{oe} of around 16 °C, 9.2% with a t_{oe} of over 16 °C and 4.3% with t_{oe} values of over 18°C.
- The Q_e matched the Q_{cd} demanded in the room. At a t_{odb} ranging from 28.3°C to 37.7°C, Q_e rose from 1.4 kW to 4.5 kW while maintaining the t_{oe} at 16 °C and the t_{j0} within the limits laid down in the RITE. The mass flow rate of the supply air was on the order of 2160 m³/h.
- The mean daily COP_{th} was 0.62, the COP_{prim_E} was 0.47 and the COP_{elec} was 5.3.
- The maximum t_{ocol} was 113 °C, while the mean daily η_{col} was 0.3 and the mean daily SCOP 0.08.

In short, the directly air-cooled chiller was observed to perform better than the commercial chiller in a number of respects.

- It could operate at a higher feed temperature ceiling (120°C) without the onset of salt crystallisation and with no need to enlarge the overall size of the prototype. This feature is particularly important when outdoor t_{odb} are high.
- The prototype generator demanded less heat. That may be because the heat regenerator in the commercial chiller was less efficient than the same component in the prototype.
- The evaporator delivered lower t_{oe} , suitable for fan coil-based air conditioning. The t_{oe} obtained with the commercial chiller was more characteristic for radiant floor cooling systems.
- The Q_e could be adjusted to the Q_{cd} in the room, with the simultaneous savings in the electric power consumed by ancillary components.
- The mean daily COP_{th} in the prototype was higher, essentially due to the lower energy demanded by the generator. Moreover, since the electric power consumed by the ancillary components was also lower, the mean daily COP_{prim_E} and COP_{elec} values were higher. The mean daily COP_{elec} proved to be comparable to the values reported for latest generation mechanical compression chillers.

Solar collector performance, in turn, was similar whether operating with the prototype or the commercial chiller, even though the collector working temperatures were 10°C higher in the latter. Flat plate vacuum collectors were shown to be a good alternative for solar-powered air-cooled single effect chillers. Finally, the mean daily SCOP values for both facilities were nearly the same at around 0.08, which is comparable to the values featured by solar-powered water-cooled absorption chillers.

In conclusion, these findings support the potential future use of solar-powered directly air-cooled absorption chillers.

Nomenclature

A	area (m ²)
COP	coefficient of performance
C _p	specific heat (kJ/kg K)
E	energy (kWh)
FTHE	fin-and-tube heat exchanger
G	solar irradiance (W/m ²)
H	solar energy (kWh/m ²)
m	mass flow rate (kg/s)
P	pump
PHE	plate heat exchanger
Q	heat transfer rate (kW)
SCF DAC P	solar cooling facility with directly air-cooled prototype
SCF IAC C	solar cooling facility with indirectly air-cooled commercial chiller
SCOP	solar coefficient of performance
t	temperature (°C)
W	electric power (kW)
X	LiBr mass fraction (%)

Subscripts

a	absorber
c	condenser
cd	cooling demand
chill	chilled
col	collector
elec	electricity
fcol	collector fluid
fsec	secondary circuit fluid
g	generator
icol	collector inlet
ie	evaporator inlet
ig	generator inlet
in	indoor
itank	tank inlet
iwcool	absorber–condenser water inlet
min	minimum
oafc	fan-coil outlet air
oair	outlet air
ocol c	ollector outlet
odb	outside dry bulb
oe	evaporator outlet
og g	enerator outlet
otank	tank outlet
owcool	absorber–condenser water outlet
prim E	primary energy
prot	prototype
t	tilted
th	thermal

Greek letters

η	efficiency
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